

CAUSES AND IMPLICATIONS OF REVENGE KILLINGS IN SOUTH SUDAN

Table of Contents

A brief Introduction	2
Revenge Killing defined.....	4
Causes of Revenge Killings in South Sudan.....	5
Implications of revenge killings in the communities	9
Recommendations to address revenge killings	11

A brief Introduction

The word revenge killing is defined as a desire for vengeance or retribution which motivated by revenge or an act or instance of retaliating in order to get evenⁱ. On the other hand, revenge killing is defined as the act of killing, injuring, or harming someone because they have harmed youⁱⁱ

When someone is wronged or hurt the first thing that comes in the mind of that person is payback in order to get even.ⁱⁱⁱ Revenge is a form of primitive justice in the ancient world in the absence of rules and regulations and organized institution to implement the said rules that governs and enable the society to be orderly, may be characterized as a form of justice but which exists outside the jurisprudence of a country's law^{iv}, revenge killing is precedent and common^v.

Revenge killing is a harmful action taken against an individual or group as retribution for the wrongs done but the funny part of it is that harm or hurt might sometimes not real just perceived. Therefore, the harmful action taken could not could be properly justified by the perpetrator of the act.^{vi} People tend to take law in their hands because of the tendency of righting the wrong and this sometimes because of the belief that culprit will not be punished.^{vii}

In line with cultural and historical conceptualization of revenge, some literature depicts that revenge is the most natural response to an act of oppression or injustice whether religiously, socially, and legally. (Schleifer, 2008).

There is a clear delineation of the word revenge killing in the ancient world, it is therefore not a new ideology but dates right from the dates of slavery and colonization of the African communities; even after the liberation of many African

states; these practices have not been stopped by some African tribes but have rather been promoted in some of the cultures in some African countries. This is evident in the context of South Sudan; incidence of revenge killings are witnessed in so many communities across the world. Starting from African, Asian, the Caribbean, the great south and European communities. But it is a very common and prevalent issue in African and it has become an area of concern, when look closely to these vicious crime that has taken up our communities, it found that revenge killings has its roots in our cultural norms and settings, more so in the way we relate to one another and the different beliefs we have developed towards each other, has created hatred towards each other. The act has also been widen by the ethnic divide created by members of the communities which has resulted to tribalistic actions within the society.

Negative Cultural and ethnic perspectives amongst people within the community has contributed too much of these killings in communities. But worse still some of these Machiavellian acts occur with members of the same ethnic groups, this mostly originate from deeply personal hatred devised toward or against a member of his tribe or another tribe because of a slight difference they have on something; in such scenario the desire to pay back for the hurt or harm done grows stronger and eventually it results to doing the unthinkable.

Some of these cultural practices that are being promoted in the community could result in such incidences of revenge killings, such practices include but not limited to forced marriages, rape and forced recruitment, robbery, cattle rustling; these are some of the practices that fuel revenge killing in the communities.

In South Sudan's case, revenge killings has become the daily rule in most communities, more especially among the cattle keeping tribes in South Sudan and one of the factor that fuels revenge killing is the issue of cattle raiding, a situation

where one tribal group attack another tribes and take their cattle, In the process of raiding, the group may end up killing people. These incidences creates a burning desire to pay back, so the process becomes vicious once triggered which is done to the detrimental effect of communities where children and women are affected negatively.

The presence of guns and ammunition amongst communities has also fueled revenge killings in South Sudan; civilians still have guns with them in the communities, this entice them to raid other communities and take their cattle's and women and children, by disarming the civilians and collecting guns own by people in such communities may stop the incidence of revenge killings and crimes committed in South Sudan; so the government arm responsible for this should develop strategies and policies of disarmament of the populace. During the SPLM war for liberation against the government of Sudan. Many children were introduced to the war and taught how to use gun to kill. This has left man ex-soldiers to have access to guns and how to use the ammunition very well, the acquisition and ownership of these guns by community has aided the process of revenge killings. From a close look of things one think the entire community is militarized, this remains a key issue to be addressed in South Sudan.

[Revenge Killing defined](#)

The term revenge killings may refer different incidences defined differently by different people in the communities and the tendency of revenge killing is very common in South Sudan; one could easily spot the influence of cultural norms and beliefs in these happenings within the communities of south Sudan; longtime ago culture has been a key factor in most traditional activities taking place in the communities; the superiority of tribes over other tribes has also been a factor that has fueled revenge. Therefore, from this angle it is very paramount for us to define

the word revenge killing; therefore revenge killing literal means “Paying back the harm, hurt, injury or injustice inflicted on one self-esteem by doing the exact harm to the person who has done it or on his nearest relation.

This is where the concept of an eye for an eye applies, a tooth for a tooth. This has become very real in the context of south Sudan due to the inter-tribal cultural differences and the raiding practices by the pastoralists tribes in the country. Most tribal groups affected by this incidence will eventually end up also indulging themselves in the practices to pay back and by doing so create a cycle that cannot be broken in the cultural beliefs of the tribes and communities involved. In most of the communities that practice revenge killings you find out that it is the young who are involved in this entire process of revenge killing and again impacted the most in the society.

Having defined revenge killings in the context of south Sudan, it is important to identify and discuss the main causes of revenge killings and crimes in our communities in South Sudan.

[Causes of Revenge Killings in South Sudan](#)

There are so many causes of revenge killings in communities around or in South Sudan these causes are categorized in different context from personal, cultural and institutional as discussed below:

Parental influence on mostly their children in the communities has help escalate the issue of revenge killings in mostly the youth engage in such acts. The bound between parents and their children are strong and parents take advantage of the bound and use it to influence their own children to seek revenge by encouraging them to pay back what has been done by other tribes against them in the community; therefore, we can see here that parental influence on the young is a key driving factor fueling revenge killing across south Sudan among the communities.

We do notice the concept of misunderstanding among tribal members also cultivate the desire to revenge amongst these parties who disagree on small issues and due to differences, they tend to magnify the issues resulting into fighting and these act in the long run creates a heart of revenge within themselves; these differences could have been sorted amicably but most resort to violent means of setting their differences this creates the continuous desire to participate or act in revenging via killing and destroying of properties.

At the occurrence of revenge killing in the community once could identify or hear the notion of delayed justice among the perpetrators of this activity in the community; people believe that institutions delivering law and justice should act first to bring the suspect to books and provide justice to the victims, however the institutions claiming to uphold law and justice are doing contrary. For instance if a suspect of a criminal act is arrested and taken to place, without the notice of the victim the suspects are in most occasion released, not tried in the courts of law; such acts are the main fabrics that creates the desire for revenge killings amongst the community members in South Sudan.

The issue of marital conflict in these communities have perpetrated revenge killings in the society. This saga involves both the young and the adult of the community. Men who suspects their wives of having secret affairs with other men within the community, would take the law in their hands and the man who is sought to have an affair with the wife, although there are extreme cases were the man murders both of the suspects and the wife because of the suspected infidelity practiced by the woman by doing these, it creates enmity between the man and his in laws, this result to bringing desire from the in law to pay back the death of their daughter hence revenge killings.

The issue of generational gap in the community has also fueled revenge killing in societies among the young and the old, so many aspects of community culture has been changed and the young generation is adopting to it and by doing so tend to spoil the cultural norms of the societies they come from and on the other hand they are labelled as being pride by the older or adult in the community leading to a deeply harbored hatred for the youth because of the generational gap between them resulting into revenge and its continued cycle.

Stress or trauma has become the cry of almost everyone or song of everyone in the community, people are being stressed by a lot of things in life and given the harsh economic situation around the economy of Juba could forcing to people to undertake revenge killing in the society for a very slight thing that could have been settled; to this is added the issue of mental disorder in the society which results to committing crimes such as killing persons, though the rate at which it influence killings is minimal , there is a great linkage between stress and mental disorder which could result to one doing the unthinkable in the society such as committing murder, rape and other evil vices in the societies of South Sudan.

People do not have the heart of forgiveness in most communities in the country, it has resulted to a continued perpetration of revenge in the societies; we are not prone to bad happenings, sad and bad things will always happening around us naturally or caused by other peopled upon us, we should in position to forgive and forget what has happened and move on with our lives in the society; revenge does not heal you or help you in any way but revives the memory of what might have happened , we should forgive and leave the rest to the hand of God to determine, however, this thought is far from many people in the communities, they are really focused on hurting the other person for what he or she has done to them, it is therefore an huge issue to continues the trend of revenge killings in the communities.

Because of the absence of peace in the society has contributed in many ways to revenge killings in rural South Sudan, whereby people take this opportunity to execute their plans of paying back whatsoever was done to them by another tribe or community members and after executing their plans, they go out clean without being noticed and brought to force the law, the absence peace in South Sudan has brought so many evil to carried out in our communities like the looting of properties, raiding, killing, forced abductions, rape and many others, it is always the right time someone to carry out his or her plan of revenging so it remains a very important cause of revenge killing in our society today.

The suffering of widows could be viewed on two ways, as a cause and an effect of revenge killing in the society; most suffering of widows are inflicted upon them by their husbands being killed or being victims of revenge killing, this explains why sometime women participate in revenge killings too, simple because of the immerse suffering they get themselves in as a result of their husband being killed by someone, in most cases these husbands are breadwinners to their families, once killed could result to suffering to the woman and the children left behind, this breeds hatred from within for the family of the perpetrators and plants deep desire to revenge until it is done or no satisfaction is derived for the victim.

There is a deeply embedded lack of respect for other peoples right and this has been cultivated due to the violent cultural practices prevalent in the community; due to the lack of respect for people rights people think they can do anything they want to anyone as they want, thus encouraging revenge killings and crimes, it is evident in most societies that people to not respect human rights or rights of other people; they tend to do what they want and think right without considering the surroundings and the law governing human associations in communities, even after committing the crimes, they are left to go scot free without facing justice.

Implications of revenge killings in the communities

The effect of revenge killings on a society are variant and it can't be fully comprehended; in analyzing impacts of revenge killings; one clearly see that the very fabric of societal existence is very much impacted , that is family, community and the economy, so it is therefore clear seen that revenge killings affects the entire community, after seeing the causes we shall later look at the suggested recommendation to put an end to this unfortunate incidence in the community that is eating our people up.

One of the effect of revenge killings is the migration or displaced of the victims household or family; as a result of this the affected people will be forced to leave the community out of fear of the unknown and relocate to a different place for safety reasons and leaving their land behind; this unplanned migration as a result of revenge killings could eventually lead to the suffering of the victims family, because by doing so they forsake their source of livelihood and forced to seek safety in IDP camps or refugees camps. Where sometimes life may not be favorable to the affected. The issue one should look at when a place is left vacant without people, the development of such a place is halted. This clearly indicates the negative impartation of revenge killings in the community.

Revenge killing results to reduction in population as a result of the killings involved, loss of lives as people die and as stated earlier, victims become scared and are forced to migrate resulting in depopulation of a particular area; in the absence of population a place cannot develop, therefore development is hindered by continued violence in the communities because people are the key factor for any development, investment or business in an area.

We also witness looting of peoples properties, destruction of properties during in the process of revenge, this negatively impacts the populace by looting and destroying

their properties, they are made vulnerable in life which leads to absolute poverty, on the other hand as properties are looted and destroyed burdens and responsibilities are increased to the affected communities, because by doing so their source of livelihood is destroyed.

Revenge killing has a negative impact on people's socialization in the communities, it destroys social relationship and when social relationship are destroyed, it affects the peaceful co-existence of people in the particular community. Mostly in executing revenge crimes and killings sons and daughters, husbands and wives are killed which creates a deeply embedded chain of hatred that is not easily broken, the killing of a beloved one cannot easily be forgotten by the family members and it becomes hard for such kind of affected people to social together in the same community, there will always be chaos in such an environment where they get themselves together. Healing in such cases is not easy people take ages to look from such traumatic experiences.

On other implication of revenge killings is that it creates insecurity for the targeted person, this result to forced migration or restricted movement for the victims for fear of being attached or assaulted by the other parties or perpetrators, when there is a restriction on one's movement, his fundamental right of movement is being abused and such restricts put a lot of things at stake; people have to move to search for means of survival or livelihood, this could result to starving ones family for fear of not being able to go and look for livelihood.

Revenge killing occurrence could result to traumatic consequences to the victim that could lead to mental disorders as a result of the killing of family members, abduction of children, rape, looting and destruction of properties; this sudden happenings could bring stress to family members and would take time for them to recover or even never recover from such experiences. Therefore, revenge killings is an evil that need to be combated before it destroys our entire communities in the country.

Recommendations to address revenge killings

There is an important role that the church has to play in South Sudan in seeing to it that the communities live peaceful among themselves. The gospel of Jesus Christ has to be preached to the populace and revenge killings should be condemned by church leaders from all denominations at all cost. When community members are preached to, the fear of the lord shall be with them and participating in such vices would be far from their thoughts otherwise it will take time for this evil to be chased out the communities.

In line with the above, the government and international organisation or even national have to support churches in developing strategies and how to implement such as a way of halting revenge killing in communities across South Sudan, the involvement of the church in this process requires funds for movement and organizing seminars, conferences where impacts will be done for the population.

The church also has a role to play in bringing cooperation and peaceful coexistence apart from other peace building organisation activities in South Sudan. The proclaiming of the good news of Jesus Christ and the gospel of love that Christ left for us, people will learn to imitate the life of Jesus Christ and therefore cooperate and co-exist peacefully in the community.

One of the fundamental recommendation to address revenge killings in the communities across South Sudan is the formation of peace dialogue team; however, the issue of concern remains how after formation can this team remain sustainable, this brings into mind the modality of the peace dialogue team at the community, what is the nature of the team formed and its composition and most important who will be responsible to undertake this process of formation for the team and ensure that people represented fairly across the community and part of the team formed to conduct dialogue forums and talks for peace purposes in the entire community.

Peace building organisations have tried their best in conducting peace dialogues in the community and done their best in bringing warring parties on the table for discussion and resolving their differences but one thing of importance that has been overlooked is the involvement of the community members and make them own the entire process because of this there is always resurgence into conflict after dialogues have been conducted by organisations and they have long left the community. Therefore, the peace dialogue team should consist of respected members of the communities such as chiefs, tribal leaders, religious leaders who are respected and listened to by their tribes or clans; by ensuring a representative composition of the community peace dialogue team, success and sustainability is secured; there is therefore a need for governmental organs and international organisations focusing on peace building to create community peace dialogue teams to ensure sustainable peace at the community level and avoid frequent resurgence into conflict after a dialogue has been conducted.

A very paramount recommendable solution to the issue of revenge killing in South Sudan is the need for awareness creation and sensitization on the dangers and impacts of revenge killings, at times the youth and other members of the community could be participating in such activities without knowing the long time consequences associated with it; if governmental organs and organisations in the peace building sector could design ways of coming up with strategies to sensitize the community on the dangers and implications of revenge killings through the use of the media like radio talks, television shows, the use of signage on billboards translated in the local language of the community would help in combating revenge killings and CSOs or CBOs could be empowered by international organisations to conduct awareness creation and sensitization on revenge killings dangers.

Engaging communities in social and communal activities that bring people together without discrimination, it promotes diversity, it creates honesty and trust among community members such activities that result to harmonious existence of community members; cutting across tribal boundaries, should be promoted by development agencies within the communities. Non-governmental organisation and CSOs can implement activities that bring community members together such activities could include sports, community communal work, dance and dramas spear headed by community leaders and encouraging youths to take part in such activities would result to making them focus and detest from participating in such crimes at all cost.

The law and order organ of the government should ensure that laws are observed and followed by civil servants, employees of the government, more especially the police officers, chiefs and judges. People who participate in such vicious activities in the communities should be brought to books and held accountable for the crimes, which they have committed in such ways people will fear to participate in such activities and also will advise their clan members to avoid taking such actions in revenge crimes and killings. Civil servants and judicial officers should detest taking briberies from suspects or their relatives. Suspects of criminal offences should be tried in the courts of law and if found guilty should be sentenced and serve their teams of sentence

ⁱ <http://www.Merriam-Webster.com>dictionary>revenge>

ⁱⁱ <https://www.collinsdictionary.com/us/dictionary/english/vengeance>

ⁱⁱⁱ Raghaven, 2007

^{iv} Schleifer, 2008

^v Majumdar, 2009

^{vi} White, 2008

^{vii} Rainsford, 2006

References

1. Majumdar, B. (2009). Eight family members beheaded in India revenge killing. Retrieved from <http://www.reuters.com/article/newsMaps/idUSTRE51A1MG20090211>
2. Raghaven, S. (2007). In the land of the blood feuds. Retrieved from <http://www.washingtonpost.com/wpdyn/content/article/2007/08/09/AR2007080902412.html>
3. Rainsford, S. (2006). The Turkish peacemaker. Retrieved from http://news.bbc.co.uk/2/hi/programmes/from_our_own_correspondent/6137236.stm
4. Schleifer, Y. (2008). In Turkey, a lone peacemaker ends many blood feuds. Retrieved from <http://www.csmonitor.com/2008/0603/p01s01-wome.html>
5. White, J. (2008). Peacemaker breaks the ancient grip of Albania's blood feuds. Retrieved from <http://www.csmonitor.com/2008/0625/p01s02-woeu.html>
6. <http://www.Merriam-Webster.com>dictionary>revenge>
7. <https://www.collinsdictionary.com/us/dictionary/english/vengeance>